

Solvent hydrogen bonding and structural effects on nucleophilic substitution reactions. Part-7 : Reaction of benzenesulphonyl chloride with substituted benzylamines in acetonitrile/dimethylsulfoxide mixtures

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Abstract : Substitution reactions of eleven *para*- and *meta*-substituted benzylamines with benzenesulphonyl chloride in different mole fractions of dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO) in acetonitrile (AcN) have been investigated conductometrically. The second order rate constants found to increase with an increase in the mole fraction of DMSO up to 0.5 mole fraction and beyond that it remained nearly constant. Multiple correlation analysis of the rate data via Kamlet-Taft's solvatochromic parameters revealed that the solvent H-bonding and dipolarity/polarizability plays a dominant role in governing the reactivity and also solvent-solvent interaction influenced the preferential solvation and consequently the rate of the reaction. A curved Hammett plot was obtained and a mechanism was proposed to account for this nonlinear behaviour observed.

Keywords : Benzylamines, benzenesulphonyl chloride, substitution reaction, solvent effect.

Introduction

Solvents play a major role in many chemical processes. Organic liquids are characterized by several properties that make them suitable for dissolving and for providing reaction media for various types of solutes. The chemical characteristics of solvent mixtures are customarily determined in the same manner as those of neat solvents by means of solvatochromic indicators. However, solute-solvent interactions are much more complex in mixed solvents than in pure solvents owing to the possibility of preferential solvation by any of the solvents present in the mixture. Moreover, the solvent-solvent interactions produced in solvent mixture can affect solute-solvent interactions and therefore preferential solvation^{1,2}.

During recent past we are interested in the study of effect of preferential solvation on nucleophilic substitution reactions of anilines³⁻⁷ as the rate of such reactions is notably affected by the solvent properties. Further, survey of literature revealed that such a study on the effect of preferential solvation on the aromatic nucleophilic substitution reactions of benzylamines is very rare. Majority of such reactions involving benzylamines were reported in neat solvents only⁸⁻¹². It is worth, therefore,

to attempt to investigate the effect of preferential solvation (in addition to structural effects) on the aromatic nucleophilic substitution reactions of benzylamines in acetonitrile (AcN)/dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO) mixtures and hence the present study.

The selection of AcN-DMSO solvent mixture for the study is based on the fact that the hydrogen bonding abilities of the mixture is well understood and among the PAHBA solvents, AcN exhibits a lower HBA ability and also exhibits a potential ability to donate a hydrogen atom towards the formation of a hydrogen bond¹³. In order to contribute to a more comprehensive analysis of the microscopic properties of binary aprotic solvent mixtures, particularly hydrogen bonding effects, it is of interest to discuss the behaviour of solvent mixtures of this type. Further, one of the profound advantages of using mixed solvents is that by varying the mole fraction of the constituent solvents, the properties of the medium can be varied in a smooth and continuous manner.

Experimental

Materials : All the chemicals (Aldrich or Merck, India) used were of analytical grade. The solvents dime-

thylsulfoxide (DMSO) and acetonitrile (AcN) were of commercially available chromatographic grade and were used as received. The solid benzylamines were used as such and the liquid benzylamines were used after vacuum distillation.

Kinetic studies : The reactions of benzenesulphonyl chloride (BSC) with substituted benzylamines in varying mole fractions of DMSO in AcN were followed conductometrically at 30, 40 and 50 ± 0.1 °C. Pseudo-first order conditions ([BSC] < [benzylamine]) were used in all cases. The reaction is so slow that it is inconvenient to wait for its completion. Therefore, the Guggenheim method¹⁴ was used to evaluate the rate constants by carrying out the kinetic runs for up to 3 h. The second order rate constants, k_A , were obtained from the observed rate constants as reported earlier¹⁵. All rate determinations were carried out at least in duplicate and the rate constants are accurate to within ±2%.

Data analysis : Correlation analyses were carried out using Microcal Origin (version 6) computer software. The goodness of the fit was discussed using correlation coefficient and standard deviation, sd ,¹⁶. The percentage contribution (P_x) of a parameter to the total effect on reactivity was computed using the regression coefficient of each parameter as reported earlier¹⁷.

Results and discussion

The nucleophilic substitution reaction of benzylamine and *para*-(Me, OMe, Cl, F, COOH, Ph) and *meta*-(Me, OMe, Cl, F) substituted benzylamines were studied conductometrically at three different temperatures in the presence of varying excess of the benzylamine over the substrate to ensure pseudo-first order kinetics. The reactions were carried out in varying mole fractions of DMSO in AcN. The overall reaction is represented as follows.

The gross mechanism of nucleophilic substitution reactions when primary and secondary amines are the nucleophiles are now well established (Scheme 1) and which involves an intermediate of the type depicted in (I).

Scheme 1

Application of steady state approximation derives the following equation, where k_A is the observed second order rate constant and B can be either a second molecule of the nucleophile or an added base.

$$k_A = \frac{k_1 (k_2 + k_3 [B])}{k_{-1} + k_2 + k_3 [B]} \quad (1)$$

The influence of [benzylamine] on the rate of the reaction was studied with an aim to determine the rate-limiting step of the reaction. The second order rate constants ($10^4 k_A, s^{-1}$) for the reaction of benzylamine with BSC (0.001 M) at 0.4 mole fraction of DMSO in AcN at 323 K were observed to be 30.4, 30.3, 30.6, 30.4 and 30.5 at [benzylamine] = 0.1, 0.15, 0.2, 0.25 and 0.3 M, respectively. The results indicated that there is no increase in the rate of the reaction with an increase in [benzylamine] and hence the reaction is not catalyzed by a base. Therefore, the formation of zwitterionic intermediate is the rate-limiting step and $k_{-1} \ll (k_2 + k_3 [B])$ in eq. (1) which is then reduced to $k_A = k_1^{18-20}$. The second order rate constants, k_A , computed for the substituted benzylamines in varying mole fractions of DMSO in AcN are summarized in Table 1.

The product analysis was carried by allowing the reactants to react for 48 h under kinetic conditions. The product was separated using medium pressure liquid chromatography and was subjected to GC-MS analysis. The results of the GC-MS analysis revealed that the reaction yielded the expected product and major fragments were shown below with their corresponding m/z ratios.

Table 1. Second order rate constants ($10^4 k_A, M^{-1} s^{-1}$) for the reaction of benzylamines with BSC in varying mole fraction of DMSO in AcN at 323 K

Substituents in benzylamine	Mole fraction of DMSO								
	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.5	0.6	0.7	0.8	0.9
None	24.6	27.6	30.1	30.4	30.4	33.1	32.6	32.0	33.1
<i>p</i> -F	25.6	30.6	32.6	32.9	34.0	34.6	34.3	34.2	34.0
<i>p</i> -Cl	19.2	22.9	24.0	25.6	27.2	27.6	27.5	27.7	27.8
<i>p</i> -Me	19.4	20.0	22.6	25.6	25.9	29.1	32.3	33.7	33.5
<i>p</i> -OMe	21.3	25.3	29.5	31.6	32.4	32.7	33.5	33.8	33.6
<i>p</i> -Ph	10.3	13.7	14.9	20.4	26.4	26.7	26.9	30.4	30.1
<i>p</i> -COOH	18.4	19.4	22.0	22.9	24.2	27.9	28.5	29.6	29.8
<i>m</i> -F	18.4	24.4	25.7	28.2	28.9	37.5	42.6	43.0	43.3
<i>m</i> -Cl	20.1	20.9	23.8	27.9	28.4	32.8	35.1	35.4	35.1
<i>m</i> -Me	16.9	23.1	24.3	28.0	30.2	30.3	33.3	34.0	34.2
<i>m</i> -OMe	18.5	22.8	24.5	25.9	26.2	26.9	27.4	28.7	28.6

313 and 323 K using the van't Hoff plot by the method of least squares and are collected in Table 2. The operation of isokinetic relationship is tested by plotting the logarithms of rate constants at two temperatures ($T_2 > T_1$) against each other according to eq. (2) as suggested by Exner²¹.

$$\log k \text{ (at } T_2) = a + b \log k \text{ (at } T_1) \quad (2)$$

In the present study linear plots implied the validity of isokinetic relationship. A representative plot is shown in Fig. 1 (in 0.4 mole fraction of DMSO, $r = 0.93$, $sd = 0.03$, isokinetic temperature = 303 ± 40 K). The operation of isokinetic relationship revealed that all the substituted benzylamines examined follow a common mechanism.

Activation parameters and the isokinetic relationship :
The activation parameters were calculated from k_A at 303,

Table 2. Effect of temperature on the rate of reaction of benzylamines with BSC in 0.4 mole fraction of DMSO and activation parameters for the reaction

Substituents in benzylamine	Rate constants $10^4 k_A, M^{-1} s^{-1}$			ΔH^\ddagger	ΔS^\ddagger	ΔG^\ddagger
	303	313	323 K			
None	20.8	25.9	30.4	12.9	-254	89.8
<i>p</i> -F	23.9	28.9	32.9	10.4	-261	89.5
<i>p</i> -Cl	19.2	22.7	25.6	9.1	-267	90.0
<i>p</i> -Me	17.4	21.2	25.6	13.1	-255	90.4
<i>p</i> -OMe	24.7	28.1	31.6	7.4	-270	89.2
<i>p</i> -Ph	14.0	17.1	20.4	12.7	-258	90.9
<i>p</i> -COOH	14.6	19.6	22.9	15.8	-247	90.6
<i>m</i> -F	16.9	21.9	28.2	18.2	-238	90.3
<i>m</i> -Cl	15.5	21.7	27.9	21.3	-228	90.4
<i>m</i> -Me	13.4	20.3	28.0	27.4	-209	90.7
<i>m</i> -OMe	17.5	21.3	25.9	13.3	-254	90.3

ΔH^\ddagger in kJ mol^{-1} ; ΔS^\ddagger in $\text{J K}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1}$; ΔG^\ddagger kJ mol^{-1} .

Fig. 1. Isokinetic plot for the reaction of benzylamines with BSC in 0.4 mole fraction of DMSO.

The activation entropies and enthalpies were also calculated for the reaction in different mole fractions of DMSO. Negative entropy of activation indicated a greater degree of ordering in the transition state than in the initial state, due to an increase in solvation during the activation process. The existence of a linear relationship (Fig. 2, $r = 0.98$, $sd = 0.02$, isokinetic temperature = 379 ± 32 K) between $\log k_A$ at 323 K and $\log k_A$ at 313 K indicated

Fig. 2. Isokinetic plot for the reaction of *p*-COOH benzylamine with BSC in all the mole fractions.

that a single mechanism is operating in all the solvent systems studied.

Solvent-reactivity correlation : The results in Table 1 revealed that increase in mole fraction of DMSO in the mixture increased the rate of the reaction up to 0.5 mole fraction of DMSO and then the rate of the reaction remained constant. The correlations of the rate data (Table 1) with relative permittivity of the medium, ϵ_r , through Laidler-Eyring²² equation and also with Reichard's polarity¹³ parameters E_T (30) were non-linear. This may be due to the fact that these solvent properties will poorly describe the microenvironment around the reacting species, which governs the stability of the transition state and hence the rate of the reaction.

Therefore, in order to obtain a deeper insight into the various solvent-solvent-solute interactions, which influence reactivity, we have tried to adopt the solvatochromic comparison method developed by Kamlet and Taft²³. The kinetic data were correlated with Kamlet-Taft's solvatochromic parameters α , β and π^* in the form of the following Linear Solvation Energy Relationship (LSER).

$$\log k = A_0 + s \pi^* + a \alpha + b \beta \quad (3)$$

where, π^* , solvent dipolarity/polarizability; α , solvent hydrogen bond donor acidity (HBD); β , solvent hydrogen bond acceptor basicity (HBA).

The regression coefficients s , a and b measure the relative susceptibilities of the solvent dependent solute property $\log k_A$ to the indicated solvent parameter. The rates of the reaction for all the compounds studied show a good correlation with solvent via the above LSER (eq. (3)) with an explained variance of $>95\%$. The above solvatochromic parameters for the solvent mixture employed in the present study were taken from the literature¹³. The statistical parameters for the correlation and the contribution of each parameter (on a percentage basis) to reactivity are listed in Table 3. The results indicated that the solvent H-bonding acidity and polarizability/dipolarity, as indicated by P_α and P_{π^*} respectively, plays a dominant role in governing the reactivity. The sign of the majority of the coefficients of these terms are negative indicating better solvation of the reactants than the transition state. With an increase in the mole fraction of DMSO in the binary mixture, as a result of preferential solvation and strong solvent-solvent interactions, the dipolarity/polarizability of the medium increases while

Table 3. Statistical results and weighted percentage contributions for the correlation of $\log k_A$ with Kamlet-Taft's solvatochromic parameters α , β and π^* at 303 K

Substituents	in benzylamine	$100R^2$	sd	a	b	s	P_α	P_β	P_{π^*}
None		96	0.01	-1.56	0.05	-1.49	50	2	48
<i>p</i> -F		96	0.01	-1.62	0.23	-1.83	44	6	50
<i>p</i> -Cl		98	0.01	-0.53	0.52	-0.52	34	33	33
<i>p</i> -Me		99	0.01	0.11	0.15	1.33	7	9	84
<i>p</i> -OMe		97	0.01	-1.03	0.60	-1.07	38	22	40
<i>p</i> -Ph		98	0.03	2.83	2.01	3.85	33	23	44
<i>p</i> -COOH		99	0.01	-0.88	0.03	0.01	96	3	1
<i>m</i> -F		97	0.03	-3.41	-0.55	-1.87	58	9	33
<i>m</i> -Cl		98	0.02	0.43	0.45	1.47	18	19	63
<i>m</i> -Me		95	0.03	-0.70	0.69	-0.26	42	42	16
<i>m</i> -OMe		95	0.02	-1.81	0.18	-1.72	49	5	46

hydrogen bond donor ability decreases with respect to ideal behaviour¹³. Hence, as a result of these two opposite effects, mainly in the DMSO rich region, no appreciable change in the rate of the reaction was observed. The observed nearly constant values of rate constants beyond 0.5 mole fraction of DMSO in the mixture may be due to the occurrence of strong solvent-solvent interactions, mainly in the DMSO rich-region, rather than solute-solvent interactions¹³. Hence, in the present study in addition to solute-solvent interaction, solvent-solvent interaction also played a vital role in governing the reactivity of benzylamines.

Structure-reactivity correlation : The effect of substituents on the rate was studied with 10 *para*- and *meta*-substituted benzylamines. The results in Table 1 revealed that in a given mole fraction, the rate constants vary with the nature of the substrate. The rate constants (k_A) calculated through the modified method is analyzed using the usual Hammett equation. A representative Hammett plot (in 0.1 mole fraction of DMSO in AcN) is shown in Fig. 3. The Hammett plot has a concave shape with a minimum for the unsubstituted benzylamine and all other benzylamines either with electron donating or electron withdrawing substituents, react faster than the parent. The observed U-shaped Hammett plot may be due to a change in the relative importance of bond formation and bond breaking in the transition state²⁴.

The correlation of the reaction rates with solvent pa-

Fig. 3. Hammett plot.

rameters via Kamlet-Taft equation indicated the existence of both solute-solvent and solvent-solvent interactions in the present study. This solvent-solvent interaction affects solute-solvent interaction to a greater extent (particularly in DMSO rich-region), and also the preferential solvation of the reacting species and consequently the rate of the reaction. Further the dipolarity/polarizability and H-bond donor ability of the solvent plays a major role in governing the reactivity. The rate constants of the reaction exhibited a curved Hammett plot. The formation of a transition state as depicted in (I) is well supported by the results of solvent and structural effects.

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